

Beyond Borders: The Role of Language in Global Research-to-Policy Dynamics

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Introduction

Governments across the globe face many complex problems. Some of these issues are applicable in other countries, while some are deeply rooted in a regional context. However, most policy issues can benefit from insight and knowledge produced elsewhere in the world. Researchers are at the forefront of knowledge production and play a crucial role in creating solutions to grand challenges. However, a significant barrier to sharing this critical knowledge being produced across the world is language. This can influence how research is translated into action across different countries and cultures.

Biases exist at every stage of research communication - issues like the Matthew Effect in citations are widely known, as well as the lack of coverage of non-English publications in research databases. This can make it difficult for research insights published in certain languages to be disseminated widely.

This study aims to understand more about the nuances to this - which languages are 'influential' and support widespread policy impact, as well as the barriers and facilitators that affect whether research gets translated into policy - to shed light on the complex process of global policymaking.

Methods and Data

Figure 1 Study Workflow

Three case studies were developed on three topics: school bullying, gender equity, and the Fukushima nuclear water discharge. Data were collected from the Overton Database, with searches completed in June 2024. Data cleaning and analysis were completed using Python in Jupyter Notebooks. The script and data are publicly shared in this OSF project: <https://osf.io/8x3gf/>.

Results

Though the case studies focused on different topics across different time periods, they uncover some trends and patterns. The following content will be described in the presentation: time from science to policy, language flows in citations, and the relationship between policy source countries and languages. In addition, examples policy-to-policy citation pathways will be discussed. An example language flows in citations figure is attached below.

Figure 2 Language Flow from Scholarly Articles to First-Gen Citing Policy Documents (Case Study I)

Discussions

International governmental organizations were found to be crucial in facilitating cross-border knowledge exchange. They serve as central conduits, translating scientific implications into policy across different languages and regions.

This study demonstrates how language impacts the reach and longevity of scholarly work in international policy discourse and emphasizes the need for a better way forward. The findings call for further research, both quantitative and qualitative, into policy-to-policy citations, as well as the exploration of factors beyond language that affect the reach and impact of research in local policy settings.

Notes: This 2-page extended abstract heavily reuses language and figures from this [blog post](#) and [report](#) produced by this research project; due to the page limit, some detailed information is not included here.